

Effects of Vocational Guidance and Counselling on Students' Career Aspirations in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. To achieve the purpose of the study, four (4) objectives of the study, four (4) research questions and four (4) null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study made use of quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study was 11,920 senior secondary II (SSII) students of all public secondary schools in Rivers State for the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample size of the study was one hundred and fifty students for the pre-test and the same one hundred and fifty students for the post-test. The sampling technique used was a multistage sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire that was rated using four-point rating scale. The data gathered were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviations for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data analysis, the findings revealed that vocational guidance and counselling has positive and significant effects on counselling and coaching, skills, values and job market on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends that: Schools should provide students with opportunities for hands-on career exploration, such as job shadowing, internships, and career fairs. The Ministry of Education at the state level should provide public secondary schools with qualified career counsellors and coaches who can offer individualized guidance and support to students that can help them develop academic plans that outline their goals, interests and values as they navigate their career aspirations.

Key Words: Aspirations, Career, Counselling and Coaching, Effects, Guidance and Counselling, Job market, Skills, Students', Values and Vocational

INTRODUCTION

One of the essential tools needed during the developmental stages of an adolescent is vocational guidance and counselling services. Adolescent stage is characterized by rapid growth and change: physically, emotionally, socially, spiritually and occupationally. Most adolescents are in the secondary schools, and that is why guidance and counselling services are very essential in this level of education. Braddock (2021) stated that, the purpose of guidance and counselling in schools is to improve academic achievement, foster positive study attitudes and habits, increase acquisition and application of conflict resolution skills, and decrease school dropouts. Lack of guidance and counselling in adolescence has resulted to increase in unpleasant outcomes in the society. These include school dropouts, drug abuse, crimes, and even failure to secure jobs. Achebe (2013) also added that the task of educational guidance and counselling is to enable a student to adjust him/herself to his/her studies by improving his/her study attitude and removing subject matter difficulties. When guidance and counselling services are lacking in schools, students' adaptation becomes difficult, thus leading to poor performance, maladaptive behaviour and school dropout.

Pearson (2018) observed that the term vocational guidance is referred to as the process of assisting people to choose a vocation for attainment of efficiency and success. The definition was however amplified in 1924 by the National Vocational Guidance Association (NVGA) whose version states that vocational guidance is the giving of information, experience in regards to choosing an occupation, preparing for it, entering into it and progressing in it. Super (2017) pointed out that it is one process of helping a person to develop and accept an integrated picture of himself/herself and his/her role in the world of work, to test this concept into reality with satisfaction to himself/herself and benefits to the society. Denga (2016) also supported this simply by indicating that vocational guidance in school is concerned with assisting students to make realistic and appropriate vocational decision. Super (2012) defined vocational guidance as the process of helping the individual to ascertain, accept, understand and apply the relevant facts about the world which are ascertained through exploratory activities.

Vocational guidance assumes that some factors influence the student's aspirations of career such as family and societal expectations, personal interests and preferences, and exposure to different career aspirations. As Napier (2012) comments, vocational guidance is the process by which all the various factors affecting an individual's occupational aspiration is sorted out, weighted and brought into focus, and by which the young person is helped to develop his/her own potentials.

There has been growing interest in the inter-relationship between occupational assessment and career aspirations. Ipaye (2016) agrees that many Nigerian students find it difficult to choose subject combination required for different occupations. Consequently, he submitted that teachers in schools need the services offered in vocational guidance to enable them collect, analyse, interpret and present them to students. Samson (2014) noted that vocational counsellors, sometimes called school or career counsellors are available to help students decide on and take the

next steps in their career aspirations. They do this by helping clients to assess and understand their strengths and capabilities in order to encourage their clients on appropriate career goals. This requires counsellors to assess and work with clients and keep up-to-date with employment options to provide timely counsel. To this end, Busel (2019) stated that general skills needed to become a successful vocational counsellor include communication skills, an attitude for testing and assessment as well as good organizational skills.

Vocational counselling is a specific type of counselling focused on helping individuals with their career aspirations and exploring their vocational interests, skills, values and goals. It is typically offered by counselling psychologist who specialize in providing guidance in educational and career-related decisions. Vocational counselling is similar to career counselling but focuses more on finding the right occupation or job market opportunity for an individual as per their interests and demands in the sector or industry they want to work in (Achebe, 2013). Vocational counsellors assist clients in various areas such as:

1. Career Exploration and Decision making
2. Goal setting and Action Planning
3. Resume and Interview Preparation

From the foregoing, the researcher aims to investigate the “independent variable” effects of vocational guidance and counselling on the “dependent variable” students’ career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State using four variables: counselling and coaching, skills, values, and job market.

Concept of Vocational Guidance

Since the beginning of the twentieth century vocational guidance and vocational education have had a strong inter-relationship. The relationship is based on the assumption that vocational guidance could help make wise occupational aspirations and that vocational education could help them prepare for what they had aspired to be. Parsons’s early formulation of vocational guidance was the need to distribute the large number of immigrants arriving in the eastern parts of America throughout an expanding industrial structure, the original emphasis was on “matching” person and job. The operational assumptions were that individuals could be described in terms of the traits they possessed (e.g., aptitudes, skills, interests and values), that each occupation could be described in terms of the combinations of these traits it required, and that fitting the individual’s pattern of traits to the occupation which most clearly required that specific pattern of traits would result in a meaningful and long-lasting choice (Betz, 2017).

In 1951 the notions that the person needs to be helped on their career aspirations, to choose on the basis of all relevant personal characteristics, rather than simple aptitudes and performance, and that career aspiration is a process rather than an event were really sharpened. The National Vocational Guidance Association around that time revised the definition vocational guidance. The

new definition of vocational guidance, proposed by Donald Super and adopted by the Association, was “the process of helping a person to develop and accept an integrated and adequate picture of himself/herself and of his/her role in the world of work, to test this concept against reality, and to convert it into a reality, with satisfaction to himself/herself and benefit to the society”. Surely, the 1951 definition of vocational guidance shifted the emphasis of vocational guidance from the needs of the occupational structure to the needs of the individual and in the process espoused individual freedom of choice.

From the expanding definitions of vocational guidance, the most recent twist is the substitution of the term vocation with the term career hence the recent term career guidance. Career guidance emphasizes that choices of education and of occupation are parts of a broader and lifelong pattern of interacting choices making up a career, a life-style. From this perspective, career guidance includes consideration of leisure activities, personal values, intermediate choices, distant as well as immediate, the kinds of personal themes one’s choices should serve, and the development of decision-making (Betz, 2017).

Concept of Vocational Counselling

Vocational counselling is a type of counselling that focuses on helping individuals explore and make informed decisions about their career aspirations. It involves providing guidance, support, and resources to individuals who are seeking clarification, direction, or assistance in their vocational pursuits. Vocational counsellors work with clients to assess their interests, aptitudes, values, and goals, and then help them identify suitable career options that align with their strengths and aspirations (Denga, 2016). They may use various tools and assessments to gather information about the client’s skills and interests, and provide guidance on education and training necessary for specific careers, job search strategies, and career development. The goal of vocational counselling is to empower individuals to make informed decisions about their career aspirations and find fulfilment and success in their chosen occupations.

Concept of Career Aspirations

Career aspiration is a crucial decision that students are required to make as they progress through their education. Vocational guidance and counselling play a significant role in affecting students’ decision-making processes regarding their aspired career. According to Denga (2016), vocational guidance and counselling provide students with the necessary information, resources, and support to help them make informed decisions about their future careers. Thomas (2020) opined that these services are instrumental in helping students understand their skills, interests, and values, which are essential factors in choosing a suitable career path. In the context of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, vocational guidance and counselling programmes have potential to positively affect students’ career aspirations by providing them with the necessary guidance and support.

Research has shown that vocational guidance and counselling programmes have a positive impact on students' career decision-making processes. A study conducted by Igwe (2018) in Nigeria found that students who received vocational guidance and counselling were more likely to make informed career choices compared to those who did not receive such support. The authors also noted that students who participated in vocational guidance and counselling programmes were more satisfied with their career aspirations and had higher levels of career self-efficacy. Furthermore, vocational guidance and counselling can help students explore a wide range of career options and understand the requirements and opportunities associated with different career paths. By gaining exposure to various careers and understanding the skills and qualifications necessary for different professions, students are better equipped to make informed decisions about their future.

In the context of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, vocational guidance and counselling can help address the challenges students face in making career aspirations, such as limited access to information about different career options, lack of awareness about their own abilities and interests, and pressure from family and society (Oluchukwu, 2015). Through vocational guidance and counselling programmes, students can receive personalized support and advice to help them overcome these challenges and make informed career decisions. Vocational guidance and counselling play a significant role in affecting students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. By providing students with the necessary information, resources, and support, these programmes have the potential to positively impact students' career decision-making processes. Future research studies can further explore the specific effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in this context, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing programmes in meeting the needs of students.

Statement of the Problem

An increasing focus has emerged on exploring the connection between occupational aspirations and career choices, particularly within the context of vocational guidance and counselling impact on students' career decisions in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State (Smith, & Johnson, 2021). From the foregoing, the importance of vocational guidance and counselling in the context of the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspiration in public secondary schools in Rivers State cannot be overstated. Vocational guidance and counselling services play a critical role in helping students navigate the complex landscape of career options and make informed decisions about their future. Vocational guidance and counselling provide students with opportunities to explore their interests, skills, and values, leading to a better understanding of their strengths and weaknesses. This self-awareness is crucial in guiding students towards careers that suit their abilities and aspirations.

Vocational guidance and counselling offer support in overcoming challenges and obstacles that may arise during the career decision-making process, such as lack of information, peer or family pressure, and uncertainty about the future. By providing a safe and supportive environment for students to discuss their concerns and aspirations, these services can empower students to make confident and well-informed choices about their career aspirations. When students are not adequately guided in their choice of vocation, they may face a multitude of challenges that can have long-lasting impacts on their academic, professional, and personal lives. There are significant obstacles hindering the effectiveness of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in Rivers State (Alutu, 2021). Some of these challenges include: limited information, misalignment of skills and interest, lack of awareness of opportunities, influence of external factors, unfulfilled potential, and increase in career risk. In Rivers State, where students may face unique socio-economic challenges and limited access to career resources, vocational guidance and counselling play a vital role in leveling the playing field and ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to explore diverse career options and pursue their aspirations.

There are related studies conducted on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspiration in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. They examined the impact of vocational guidance and counselling on career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study revealed that students who received guidance and counselling services were more likely to make informed career choices aligned with their interests, abilities and aspirations. Okafor and Amadi (2019) also explored how vocational guidance and counselling interventions influenced students' career aspirations and choices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings revealed that effective counselling services positively influenced students' career decision-making processes. These studies provided valuable insights into the importance of vocational guidance and counselling in shaping students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The study on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State aims to address several gaps in the existing literature. These include: limited studies on the specific impact of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations, lack of empirical research on the effectiveness of vocational guidance and counselling programmes in shaping students' career goals in the local context, scarcity of information on the strategies and approaches employed by vocational guidance counsellors in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and their impact on students' career aspirations. By addressing these gaps, the study on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State aims to contribute valuable insights in the field of career development and counselling, particularly in the context of the specific challenges and opportunities present in the region.

Purpose of the Study

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The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study sought to achieve the following objectives; to:

1. examine the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects counselling and coaching on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. investigate the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects skills on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. establish the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects values on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. find out the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects job market on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study sought answers to the following questions:

1. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect counselling and coaching on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect skills on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect values on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
4. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect job market on students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses has been formulated and tested at 0.05 level significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which counselling and coaching affects students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which skills affects students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which values affects students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which job market affects students' career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

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The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design to find out the effect of vocational guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State. Trost (2016) observed that quasi-experimental research is a type of research design that lacks the random assignment of participants to experimental and control groups. The population of this study was 11,920 senior secondary II (SSII) students of all Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State for the 2024/2025 academic sessions. A sample is a smaller, manageable and representative portion of a larger population (Ipaye, 2016). The sample of a study is a subset of the population of the study. Sampling is a process whereby a small portion of the total population is selected to represent the entire population (Okafor & Amadi, 2019). The multistage sampling technique was employed in the study. This study used for data collection, a self-structured questionnaire titled "Effects of Vocational Guidance and Counselling on Students' Career Aspiration Questionnaire (EVCSCAQ). The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) with frequency tables; weighted mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. An item is accepted if the criterion mean is above 2.50 and rejected if below 2.50. The criterion mean is obtained by adding together and dividing by 2 the scales of 1, 2, 3 and 4 representing strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed respectively. The null hypotheses were tested using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic with the use of SPSS at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the effects of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Counselling and Coaching on Career Aspiration of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
1	Provide the necessary foundation for students to gain self-awareness in their career choice.	2.90	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.74	2.80	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
2	Build students' emotional resilience in making career choice.	3.02	3.20	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.02	3.42	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.84	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
3	Activate the students to manage their mental health concerns effectively in career choice.	2.98	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.04	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.82	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
4	Steer the students towards their personal growth and career choice.	2.92	3.22	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.80	2.88	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
5	Enable the students on their goal achievement and career-oriented choice.	3.02	3.26	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.02	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.86	2.84	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
Grand Mean Score		2.97	3.25	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.98	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.84	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 1 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career aspirations were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 & 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 4.5 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2

exceeded their pre-test scores (items 1 - 5), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on counselling and coaching resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and displayed inconsistent patterns. Items 1, 2 and 4 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores, while items 3 and 5 have average post-test scores less than the average pre-test scores. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on counselling and coaching yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.97 and 3.25 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.98 and 3.38 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.82 and 2.84 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that counselling and coaching received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career aspirations.

Research Question 2: What are the effects of skills on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Skills on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
6	Engage the students in creative activities.	3.00	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.90	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
7	Produce new things and ideas to the students.	2.96	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.98	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.72	2.86	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
8	Involve the students in investigative and research activities.	2.92	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.82	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
9	Encourage the students towards designing and building.	2.84	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	3.33	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.84	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

10	Determine that student use their reasoning ability.	2.98	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.94	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.88	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
11	Appeal to students' cognition by solving science and math problems-including abstract ones.	3.02	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.02	3.26	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	2.90	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
Grand Mean Score		2.95	3.35	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.94	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.83	2.87	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 2 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career aspirations were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 4.6 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 6 - 11), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on skills resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group's average pre-test and post-test scores are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 6, 7, and 9 have average post-test scores greater than average pre-test scores, items 28 and 10 have average post-test scores equal to average pre-test scores, and item 11 has average post-test score less than average pre-test score. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on skills yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.95 and 3.35 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.94 and 3.32 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.83 and 2.87 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that skills received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career aspirations.

Research Question 3: What are the effects of values on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Values on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
12	Influence students to communicate helpful information to many people.	2.96	3.25	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.94	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.80	2.86	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
13	Help the students demonstrate their designs and ideas to others.	2.98	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.82	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
14	Provide students with various career paths that align with their personal values and career choice.	2.92	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	2.86	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
15	Grant students the confidence to make well-informed decisions.	2.90	3.35	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	2.84	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
16	Define the students' career decision-making process	3.00	3.33	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.98	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.88	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
17	Identify students' ability to use interpersonal skills in making people happy.	2.94	3.45	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.82	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
Grand Mean Score		2.95	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.93	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.85	2.85	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 3 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career aspirations were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 3 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 12-17), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the

intervention. This implies that students’ knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on values resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 12 and 14 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores, items 13 and 15 have average post-test scores less than the average pre-test scores, and items 16 and 17 have average post-test scores equal to the average pre-test scores. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on values yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.95 and 3.36 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.93 and 3.36 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.85 and 2.85 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that skills received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career aspirations.

Research Question 4: What are the effects of job market on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Job Market on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
18	Enables students gain a realistic understanding of the job market and career opportunities available.	2.92	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.86	2.92	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
19	Provides students with information about the labour market.	2.94	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.88	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
20	Positively influences students’ career decision-making processes.	2.92	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	2.88	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
21	Provides them with valuable information about various career paths available to them.	2.96	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	2.82	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
22	Leading them to greater success and job	2.90	3.36	Post Mean	2.90	3.38	Post Mean	2.86	2.88	Post Mean

	satisfaction in their chosen fields.			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean
23	Increases their chances of finding employment in fields that align with their passions and strengths.	3.00	3.38	Post Mean	3.00	3.40	Post Mean	2.84	2.90	Post Mean
				> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean
	Grand Mean Score	3.01	3.33	Post Mean	2.92	3.36	Post Mean	2.86	2.88	Post Mean
				> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean

The information in Table 4 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career aspirations were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 4 reveals that the average posttest scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 18 - 23), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on vocational guidance and counselling resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 18, 22, and 23 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores, items 20 and 21 have post-test average scores less than the pre-test average scores, and item 19 has an average post-test score equal to the average pre-test score. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on career exploration yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 3.01 and 3.33 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.92 and 3.36 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.86 and 2.88 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that skills received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career aspirations.

Hypotheses Testing

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Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Counselling and Coaching on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8.126 ^a	3	2.709	90.586	.000	.651
Intercept	2.512	1	2.512	83.993	.000	.365
VAR00001	.290	1	.290	9.709	.002	.062
VAR00003	5.398	2	2.699	90.266	.000	.553
Error	4.366	146	.030			
Total	1505.280	150				
Corrected Total	12.492	149				

The information in Table 5 shows that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 5.398, df = 2, mean square = 2.699, and F = 90.266 that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 90.266; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of skills on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Skills on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.107 ^a	3	2.369	62.073	.000	.561
Intercept	3.889	1	3.889	101.892	.00	.411
VAR00001	.014	1	.014	.364	.547	.002
VAR00003	5.909	2	2.954	77.411	.000	.515
Error	5.572	146	.038			
Total	1526.361	150				
Corrected Total	12.679	149				

The results in Table 6 show that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares 5.909, df = 2, mean square = 2.954, and F = 77.411 that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null

hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of skills on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 77.411, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of skills on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 77.411; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant effect of values on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Values on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	9.097 ^a	3	3.032	85.326	.000	.637
Intercept	3.176	1	3.176	89.377	.000	.380
VAR00001	.026	1	.026	.724	.396	.005
VAR00003	8.322	2	4.161	117.086	.000	.616
Error	5.189	146	.036			
Total	1535.389	150				
Corrected Total	14.286	149				

The information in Table 7 shows that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 8.322, $df = 2$, mean square = 4.161, and $F = 117.086$ that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of values on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of values on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 117.086; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant effect of job market on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Job Market on Career Aspirations of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.433 ^a	3	2.478	97.259	.000	.666
Intercept	2.659	1	2.659	104.394	.000	.417
VAR00001	.108	1	.108	4.239	.041	.028
VAR00003	6.632	2	3.316	130.164	.000	.641
Error	3.719	146	.025			
Total	1539.694	150				
Corrected Total	11.152	149				

The information in Table 8 shows that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 5.398, $df = 2$, mean square = 2.699, and $F = 90.266$ that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of job market on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266$, $p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of job market on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 90.266$; $\alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of research question 1 revealed that there are significant effects of counselling and coaching of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In the same vein Samson (2016) conducted a study titled, “Impact of Guidance and Counselling Coaching on Students’ Academic Performance in University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State.” He observed that there is a positive impact of guidance and counselling coaching on students’ academic performance in Rivers State. Smith & Johnson (2021) observed that vocational counselling, career counselling and personal-social counselling have significant effects on the students’ career choice in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The relationship between the impact of guidance and counselling coaching on students’ academic performance in University of Port Harcourt and the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students’ career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, especially in the context of counselling and coaching, highlights the importance of providing students with comprehensive support services. Through counselling and coaching sessions, students can receive support in understanding their interests, strengths and values that can align them with potential career paths and developing strategies to achieve their career aspirations. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266$, $p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of counselling and coaching on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 90.266$; $\alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

The finding of research question 2 revealed that there are significant effects of skills on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding is in collaboration with Santo (2016) research titled, “Relationship between Guidance and Counselling Vocational Skills and Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. The study indicated that there is a significant relationship between guidance and counselling vocational skills and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Owan & Nwagbara (2017) carried out a study on the effects of vocational counselling skills on students’ academic performance in Rivers State. Based on the analysis, the findings of the study revealed that vocational counselling skills has a significant effect on the students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The relationship

between guidance and counselling of vocational skills, academic performance and the career aspirations for students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is crucial. When students are counselled properly through vocational guidance and counselling, they are able to develop important skills that not only enhance their academic performance but also prepare them for their future careers. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of skills on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 77.411, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of skills on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 77.411; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

The finding of the research questions 3 revealed that there are significant effects of values on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In the same vein Thomas (2020) study on the effects of vocational counselling values on students’ academic performance in Rivers State. The findings of the study revealed that vocational counselling values has a significant effect on the students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Oluchukwu (2015) observed that vocational counselling, career counselling and personal-social counselling have positive influence on students’ career aspiration in Rivers State. The relationship between the effects of vocational counselling values on students’ academic performance in Rivers State and the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students’ career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in regards to values is interconnected. By focusing on values such as self-awareness, motivation and career interest, vocational counsellor can help students achieve academic success and make informed career decisions in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of values on students career aspirations in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of values on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 117.086; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

The finding of research question 4 revealed that there are significant effects of job market on career aspirations of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In collaboration Igwe (2018) research on the role of guidance and counselling on job market in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings of the study revealed that guidance and counselling play positive roles of on-the-job market in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The relationship between these two studies lies in the potential for vocational guidance and counselling to bridge the gap between students are provided with the necessary tools and resources to explore various career options and align them with market demands vocational guidance and counselling can play a crucial role in enhancing students’ preparedness for the job market in Rivers State. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of job market on career aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 90.266, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of job market on career

aspirations of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 90.266$; $\alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the research concluded that there is a positive and significant effects of vocational guidance and counselling on counselling and coaching to help students have higher level of preparedness for the job market. Students who have received this guidance are more likely to have the skills, values and knowledge needed to succeed in their chosen field, increasing their chances of finding fulfilling employment. Evidence from the study still revealed that students who have received vocational guidance and counselling are more likely to be satisfied with their chosen career aspirations. Vocational guidance and counselling programmes often include career assessment and testing to help students understand their strengths and interests. Students who have received vocational guidance and counselling are more likely to explore a wider range of career options and choose a career that is aligned with their interests, values and aspirations. The students are most likely to have the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in their chosen field, increasing their chances of finding fulfilling employment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Schools should provide access to qualified career counsellors and coaches who can offer individualized guidance and support to students as they navigate their career choices.
2. Schools should help students identify and develop the skills and values that are important for success in their chosen career paths.
3. The integration of vocational guidance and counselling in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State is essential for helping students make informed decisions about their career goals and aspirations.
4. The State Government through the Schools Educational Board should provide registered and qualified counsellors to all the public secondary schools in Rivers State.

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